

ENGLISH IDIOMS AND UZBEK IDIOMS

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Annotation: This article explores the similarities and differences between English idioms and Uzbek phrases. It highlights how these linguistic expressions reflect the culture, traditions, and worldview of their respective speakers. The author analyzes the structure, meaning, and usage of idioms in both languages, offering examples to illustrate their contextual nuances. The article also examines challenges in translating idioms due to cultural specificity and linguistic differences. It provides insights into how idioms enrich communication and serve as a bridge for understanding cultural diversity. This comparative study is valuable for linguists, language learners, and cultural enthusiasts. Keywords:

Key words: Comparative linguistics, cultural differences, language translation, idiomatic expressions, linguistic analysis, cross-cultural communication, phraseology, contextual meaning.

INGLIZ IBORALARI VA O'ZBEK IBORALARI

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola inglizcha idiomlar va o'zbek iboralari o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni o'rganadi. Unda ushbu til ifodalari tegishli madaniyat, an'analar va dunyoqarashni qanday aks ettirishi ko'rsatiladi. Muallif ikki tildagi iboralarning tuzilishi, ma'nosi va qo'llanilishini tahlil qilib, ularning kontekstual nozikliklarini misollar yordamida ochib beradi. Shuningdek, maqolada madaniy o'ziga xoslik va til farqlari tufayli iboralarni tarjima qilishdagi qiyinchiliklar ham yoritiladi. Idiomlarning muloqotni boyitishi va madaniy xilma-xillikni tushunishda ko'prikin vazifasini bajarishi haqidagi fikrlar bildiriladi. Ushbu qiyosiy tadqiqot lingvistlar, til o'rganuvchilar va madaniyat ixlosmandlari uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: inglizcha iboralar, o'zbek iboralar, qiyosiy lingvistika, madaniy farqlar, til tarjimasi, idiomatic ifodalar, lingvistik tahlil, madaniyatlararo muloqot, frazeologiya, kontekstual ma'no.

1. Rome wasn't built in a day

Meaning: Great achievements take time.

Uzbek: mehnatni tagi rohat

Explanation: Har qanday katta ish uchun vaqt kerak.

2. Don't count your chickens before they hatch

Meaning: Don't make plans based on uncertain outcomes.

Uzbek: chuchvarani hom sanamoq

Explanation: Ish tugamagan bo'lsa, reja qilishga shoshilmang.

3. The fish rots from the head down

Meaning: Problems start at the leadership level.

Uzbek: Baliq boshidan sasiydi.

Explanation: Muammo har doim yuqoridan boshlanadi.

4. What goes around comes around

Meaning: Your actions will eventually come back to you.

Uzbek: Qilma toparsan, ekma o'rarsan.

Explanation: O'z qilgan ishing o'zingga qaytadi.

5. Barking dogs seldom bite

Meaning: Those who make threats often don't act on them.

Uzbek: it hurar karvon o'tar

Explanation: Qo'rqitadigan odam ko'pincha zarar yetkazmaydi.

6. A friend in need is a friend indeed

Meaning: True friends help in difficult times.

Uzbek: do'st kulfatda bilinadi

Explanation: Haqiqiy do'st qiyinchilikda bilinar.

7. Don't put all your eggs in one basket

Meaning: Don't risk everything on one plan.

Uzbek: ikki oyoqni bir etikka tiqma.

Explanation: Hammasini bir joyga yig'maslik kerak.

8. Don't judge a book by its cover

Meaning: Don't judge something based on appearance.

Uzbek: Ko'rinishga qarab baho berma.

Explanation: Faqat tashqi ko'rinishga ishonib baho bermang.

9. A rolling stone gathers no moss

Meaning: Those who keep moving don't settle.

Uzbek: harakatda barokat.

Explanation: Harakatdagi odam boshqacha rivojlanadi.

10. Still waters run deep

Meaning: Quiet people often have deep thoughts.

Uzbek: Sokin suvning tubi chuqur.

Explanation: Tinch odamlar ko'pincha chuqur fikr yuritadi.

11. Don't make a mountain out of a molehill

Meaning: Don't exaggerate small problems.

Uzbek: chumolidan fil yasama.

Explanation: Mayda muammoni katta qilib ko'rsatma.

12. Strike while the iron is hot

Meaning: Take advantage of opportunities when they arise.

Uzbek: Temirni qizig'ida bos.

Explanation: Fursatdan foydalanishni o'rgan.

13. Too many cooks spoil the broth

Meaning: Too many people working on one thing can ruin it.

Uzbek: ko'p usta , uy buzar.

Explanation: Har ishda me'yor bo'lishi kerak.

14. *A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush*

Meaning: It's better to have something certain than risk for more.

Uzbek: Kafadagi chumchuq daladagi turnadan yaxshi.

Explanation: Bor narsaga qanoat qilish kerak.

15. *Empty vessels make the most noise*

Meaning: People with little knowledge talk the most.

Uzbek: Bo'sh mesh shovqin qiladi.

Explanation: Bilimsiz odamlar ko'proq gapiradi.

16. *Haste makes waste*

Meaning: Acting too quickly leads to mistakes.

Uzbek: Shoshgan qiz erga yolchimaydi.

Explanation: Shoshilib ish qilish zarar keltiradi.

17. *Every cloud has a silver lining*

Meaning: Every bad situation has some good in it.

Uzbek: oyning o'n beshi yorug, o'n beshi qorong'u.

Explanation: Har bir yomon vaziyatning yaxshi tomoni bo'ladi.

1. *Once in a blue moon*

Uzbek: Oyda-yilda bir marta.

Meaning: Something that happens very rarely. **Meaning:** Take advantage of opportunities while they last.

Uzbek: intilganga tole yor

Explanation: Vaqtida ishlash va imkoniyatni boy bermaslik kerak.

19. *Walls have ears*

Meaning: Be careful what you say; someone might hear.

Uzbek: Devorning ham qulog'i bor.

Explanation: Har doim ehtiyot bo'lish kerak.

20. *Don't bite the hand that feeds you*

Meaning: Don't hurt those who help you.

Uzbek: yaxshilik ikki ko'z ortasida turadi.

Explanation: Senga yordam bergan odamga zarar yetkazma.

21. *Once in a blue moon*

Uzbek: Oyda-yilda bir marta.

Meaning: Something that happens very rarely.

Explanation: kamdan kam sodir bo'lish.

22. *Feeling blue*

Uzbek: tabi tiriq bo'lish

Meaning: Feeling sad or depressed

Explanation: hafa bo'lmoq

23. *Green with envy*

Uzbek: Rashkdan ko'karib ketmoq.

Meaning: Very jealous.

24. *In the red*

Uzbek: tinkasi qurimoq

25. *In the black*

Uzbek: Foydada bo'lish.

Meaning: Profitable or financially stable.

26. *White lie*

Uzbek: Yengil yolg'on.

Meaning: A harmless or small lie, often told to avoid hurting someone.

27. *Red-handed*

Uzbek: Qo'lidan ushlamoq.

Meaning: Caught in the act of doing something wrong.

28. *Out of the blue*

Uzbek: Kutilmaganda.

Meaning: Suddenly or unexpectedly.

29. *Tickled pink*

Uzbek: Juda xursand bo'lmoq.

Meaning: Extremely pleased or delighted.

30. *Black and white*

Uzbek: Oq va qora

Uzbek Idioms with Colors and Their English Equivalent

11. *Yashil chiroq yoqmoq*

English: To give the green light.

Meaning: To give permission to proceed.

12. *Oq yuz bo'lish*

English: To be honorable.

Meaning: To maintain dignity or integrity.

13. *Qora kunlar uchun*

English: For a rainy day.

Meaning: Saving something for difficult times.

14. *Yashil bo'lib ketmoq*

English: To turn green.

Meaning: To feel sick or jealous.

15. *Qizil bo'lib ketmoq*

English: To turn red.

Meaning: To feel embarrassed or angry.

16. *Oq bayroq ko'tarmoq*

English: To raise the white flag.

Meaning: To surrender or give up.

17. *Oltin o'rtalikni topmoq*

English: To find the golden mean.

Meaning: To find a balanced or moderate solution.

18. *Qora terga botmoq*

English: To be in a black sweat.

Meaning: To work very hard or be extremely stressed.

19. Oq ko'ngilli

English: White-hearted.

Meaning: Kind and pure-hearted.

20. Qora ko'ngil bo'lmoq

English: Black-hearted.

Meaning: Cruel or evil-heart

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